

Table A1. Results of unit root tests

Country dependent variables	Levels		Differences	
	ADF-GLS	KPSS	ADF-GLS	KPSS
FRANCE				
CO2	0.52 (c)	0.8*** (c)	-5.77*** (c)	0.10 (c)
GDP	0.66 (c)	0.2*** (c)	-3.50*** (c)	0.05 (c)
NUCLEAR	-1.87 (c+t)	0.2*** (c+t)	-3.97*** (c+t)	0.09 (c+t)
RES	0.83 (c)	0.22*** (c+t)	-2.80*** (c)	0.08 (c+t)
SPAIN				
CO2	-0.32 (c)	0.78*** (c)	-5.72*** (c)	0.45*(c)
GDP	0.14 (c)	0.9*** (c)	-2.81*** (c)	0.19 (c)
NUCLEAR	-0.76 (c+t)	0.22*** (c+t)	-2.94* (c+t)	0.07 (c+t)
RES	0.52 (c)	0.89*** (c)	-4.76*** (c)	0.11 (c)
SWEDEN				
CO2	0.35 (c)	0.77*** (c)	-6.67*** (c)	0.14 (c)
GDP	0.54 (c)	0.79*** (c)	-4.84*** (c)	0.09 (c)
NUCLEAR	-0.94 (c)	0.18** (c+t)	-6.15*** (c)	0.17** (c+t)
RES	1.11 (c)	0.81*** (c+t)	-3.32*** (c)	0.07 (c)

Note: c and t stand for constant and linear trend; ***, **, * indicate the significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.